

22. Communities of Practice: The Importance of Collective Viewpoints for Sustainable Agri-food Systems

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1. Introduction

Our planet currently sits at the nexus of an enormous and dichotomous concern: how do we ensure the health and prosperity of 8 billion people while ensuring the sustainability and viability of our ecosystems? On the one hand, the ability to grow grains in high quantities has massively reduced the starvation and malnourishment of our world's population. At the same time, the current practices used are not sustainable. Yet while our traditional methods are sustainable, they are not scalable. The real dilemma is to connect these two strategies at the production and consumption sides. According to a report by the IUCN (Oberć and Schnell 2020), sustainable agriculture must first consider two inseparable, intertwined societal priorities – preserving the environment and providing safe and healthy food for all.

Achieving food security through sustainable practices in the Global South faces many concerns, including population growth, urban migration, poverty, social inequalities, fluctuations in the market, and depletion of natural resources. These issues, though all interconnected, look different when viewed from different lenses. Smallholder farmers in Asia and sub-Saharan Africa provide up to 80% of the food supply (FAO, 2012). Meanwhile, the average farmer owes up to 60% of their income in debt (MoSPI 2021a, 2021b), and an estimated 40% of the food they produce does not reach our tables due to loss in production, processing, and/or distribution (FAO, 2022). Amidst these concerns, agricultural systems need to feed an ever-increasing population whose food demands are projected to double over the next 50 years (HOW2050 2009). These concerns and the adverse impacts of climate change have threatened our food security. In 2020, 45.4 million children under five were impacted by malnutrition, 17% of which live in India (UNICEF *et al.*, 2021). Food systems are locked in a spiral of decline with environmental systems: they are also significant causes of degradation of the ecological systems on which they depend.

Systems-level solutions that work for every sector and individual in the process are needed. These solutions must be human-centred, which means they need to consider the social, cultural, and historical context wherever they are implemented. A collaborative approach is required that considers the view points of each stakeholder in the system, identifies common interests and points of inflexion and establishes communities of practice (Wenger-Trayner and Wenger-Trayner 2015) that work iteratively together across the system. These communities of practice must learn from each other, cocreate standard solutions, and iteratively enhance solutions through regular interaction and reevaluation of the process.

To begin the development of such communities, we

present the biggest challenges in sustainable food systems through the perspectives of the three corners of the food systems triangle in India: the producers, the consumers, and the environment itself. Here we offer key recommendations and examples adapted from our recent white paper (Paroda *et al.*, 2022) that all stakeholders in the agricultural system can use to identify a common path that embraces both food and environmental security sustainably.

2. Discussion

2.1 The producer's perspective

In India, agricultural economy and food security depend primarily on smallholder farmers. Roughly 86% of farmers in India are smallholder farmers (including marginal farmers) who own 47% of the crop area (MoAFW 2020). Despite this contribution, smallholder families, who constitute about one-half of the national population, comprise almost three-fifths of the nation's hungry and poor. Therefore, it is socially beneficial that agricultural lands with smaller land holdings and their farmers are supported to adopt sustainable practices that increase productivity for themselves and their communities and, at the same time, conserve the environment. However, the complication of transitioning to sustainable practices arises in bringing the benefits of finances, technologies, and scale to these small landholdings.

Financial benefits are limited due to a need for product marketing and capital for organic farm inputs. Many investments have been initiated by government and bilateral agencies, private donors, and investors. Yet CoSAI research (CoSAI 2020) shows that only a tiny fraction of such funding is intended to promote environmental and social objectives.

Technologies must provide better logistical linking of producers to consumers to minimise post-harvest losses, greater responsiveness to consumer needs, and accessibility to solutions promoting sustainable food systems. As production and value chain systems become increasingly digitised, farmers should be empowered to gain more revenue from the food they produce and the knowledge they bring to the process within these digital spaces. Farmers can be trained to use agricultural apps, participate in policy-making decisions, interpret meteorological data, analyse consumer patterns, and other participatory interventions. We also need to increase their digital literacy to ensure they take advantage of connectivity to reach consumers as directly as possible and with virtual support networks.

Finally, to address scale and maintain the value chain, we need more local and contextualised market solutions for different localities, agricultural practices, stakeholders, landscapes, and other conditions. We need to develop mechanisms to create regional funds and focus on bringing diverse investors and donors together locally to create the

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ecosystem required for farmers to flourish, particularly small and marginal farmers. Stakeholder consultations that involve key decision makers from the government and corporate sectors can help influence the implementation of programs with mechanisms that increase farmers' incomes and can be scaled. Farmers could be incentivised directly to adopt sustainable approaches through direct account transfers. Unless our producers are empowered with increased revenues and capabilities, our proposed recommendations and techniques will not be implemented successfully.

2.2 The consumer's perspective

In 2018, the Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO) and the United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP) jointly framed sustainable agriculture as "a consumer-driven, holistic concept that refers to the integrated implementation of sustainable patterns of food consumption and production" (FAO and UNEP 2022). Consumers worldwide can be a powerful force for change towards more sustainable and equitable agri-food systems. However, marketing approaches view consumers as passive actors, deepening the disconnect between consumers, producers, and nature.

From a market perspective, communication strategies should encourage the consumption of healthy, nutritious, and sustainable food as aspirational for all. Policies can be framed to promote green lifestyles in circular bioeconomies. Simultaneously, mechanisms must be established to ensure that food is economically accessible to consumers. Studies on consumer behaviour show that people in India are willing to spend a premium price for organically grown and sustainably sourced food. Still, their purchase intention is chiefly affected by accessibility and availability, amongst other factors (Singh and Verma, 2017).

Consumers must also play an active role in the sustainable transition. For example, including both producers and consumers in the production and distribution process can collectively allow both parties to peer review the production process and ensure that the producer abides by the criteria and standards that guarantee the quality and integrity of the product. Such inclusion leads to equal sharing of power and responsibilities, the formation of trust, and a permanent learning process through the engagement of all stakeholders.

From being the largest drivers of global environmental change to becoming agents of global sustainability, the transition to more sustainable practices requires a significant shift from farm-level solutions to focusing on the entire value chain - uniting producers and consumers in all our discussions. Most agricultural value chains are outlined in a linear format, placing consumers at the end of the value chain. However, consumers directly impact not just the market but also the producers and the environment. In the entire value chain, consumers can disrupt the system towards more sustainable and equitable agri-food systems.

2.3 The environment perspective

Historically, we have approached agriculture primarily from an extractive and intensive approach to increase productivity for the ever-growing population. These approaches have led to the degradation of the ecosystems on which agriculture inherently depends. It is estimated that 33% of the world's soils have been degraded (FAO and ITPS 2015). Three additional challenges that are being faced today are the ecosystem services on which agriculture depends, the health of biodiversity, and climate change. In most countries across the Global South and particularly in India, cultivation patterns such as mono-cropping with heavy reliance on groundwater and chemical inputs have reduced food

sovereignty and have added to growing environmental problems. In addition, these farming methods have decreased the carbon-sequestering ability of soil, which is one of the reasons for our increasing global temperatures. As a specific example, healthy soils potentially hold up to 50 times more water than chemically driven agricultural soils (Kumar and Jehne, 2020). Increased soil water-holding capacity decreases the chances of floods. Healthy soil also promotes the soil's ability to sequester carbon. Therefore, farmers will suffer less from a low-yield season than conventional chemical-based farming because of better carbon sequestration and soil resilience.

For finance ministries, incentivising sustainable agricultural practices is critical regarding food security, biodiversity conservation, and the overall well-being of humans, animals and the larger ecosystem. Incentives should be advocated not only by the ministers themselves but by governments at national and international levels. It is also essential to ensure that government schemes and strategies are adapted across various agroecological zones. Better adaptation of policies for agroecological considerations in India could be achieved through effective implementation of programs and activities under the National Action Plan on Climate Change (NAPCC; DBT 2008), National Water Mission (NWM 2020), National Mission for a 'Green India' (MoEFCC 2022), National Mission for Sustainable Agriculture (MoAFW 2019), and the proposed National Mission on Biodiversity and Human Wellbeing (PSA 2020). Important policy areas include rural development (e.g., guaranteed employment for the rural poor for part of the year, investment in rural infrastructure); spatial planning (e.g., land use planning, zoning regulations); environmental regulations (e.g., strategic environmental assessments); water policies and planning (e.g., integrated water resources management approaches, water tariffs); agricultural pricing (e.g., tariffs, minimum price guarantee, and subsidies for agricultural commodities); and risk management (contingency plans, insurance, seed banks). The policies of local and national governments directly contribute to adapting various schemes and strategies across different agroecological zones.

Through community consultations with farming communities, researchers and local environmental experts can work together to identify gaps and develop guidelines and toolkits that are contextualised and region-specific. Advancing agroecology requires harnessing the power of a social movement and knowledge-intensive practices. Both must be intrinsically linked for success to happen.

3. Conclusions

Social, economic, and environmental sustainability are closely intertwined and necessary for sustainable food systems. Farmers faced with poverty are often forced to mine natural resources to make ends meet, even though environmental degradation may affect their long-term livelihood. Consumers, who in most cases are placed at the end of the traditional linear agri-supply chain, play an essential role in the transition to sustainable food systems. Consumption patterns regulate markets and farm production while determining the nature of the waste and side streams produced in the process that can be used as inputs for subsequent production. On the other hand, the behavioural aspects of consumers can also negatively impact the soil, water, biodiversity, and climate inputs for producers. Understanding the interrelationships between the various actors and stakeholders in our agriculture and food systems is important. By creating policies and practices that integrate social, environmental, and economic interests, societies can promote more sustainable food security. There is enormous

power when all stakeholders come together. Listening and learning how to trust each other is just the beginning. We need to turn networks into communities of practice that share, multiply, expand and scale knowledge.

References

- CoSAI. Commission on Sustainable Agricultural Intensification 2020. Emerging evidence from CoSAI's studies and activities. <https://wle.cgiar.org/cosai/evidence>.
- DBT. Department of Science and Technology 2008. National action plan on climate change (NAPCC). <https://dst.gov.in/climate-change-programme>.
- FAO. Food and Agriculture Association of the United Nations 2012. Smallholders and family farmers. <https://www.fao.org>.
- FAO. Food and Agriculture Association of the United Nations 2022. Seeking end to loss and waste of food along production chain. <https://www.fao.org>
- FAO. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, and ITPS, Intergovernmental technical panel on soils. 2015. Status of the World's Soil Resources (SWSR)- Main Report. <https://www.fao.org>
- FAO. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, and UNEP, United Nations Environment Programme 2022. The FAO-UNEP sustainable food systems programme. <https://www.fao.org>
- HOW2050. High level expert forum (How to feed the world in 2050). 2009. Global agriculture towards 2050. <https://www.fao.org>.
- Kumar V and Walter J. 2020. Andhra Pradesh community managed natural farming. <https://soilcarboncoalition.org>
- MoAFW. Agriculture Census Division Department of Agriculture Cooperation and Farmers Welfare Ministry of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare 2020. All India report on agriculture census 2015-16. <https://agcensus.nic.in>
- MoAFW. Ministry of Agriculture & Farmers Welfare. 2019. National mission for sustainable agriculture. <https://nmsa.dac.gov.in/>.
- MoEFCC. Ministry of Environment Forest and Climate Change 2022. Targets sets under Green India Mission. <https://pib.gov.in>
- MoSPI. National Statistical Office Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation. 2021a. Situation assessment of agricultural households and land and holdings of households in rural India, 2019. <https://www.mospi.gov.in>
- MoSPI. National Statistical Office Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation. 2021b. All India debt and investment survey (January–December, 2019).
- NWM. National Water Mission 2020. National water mission. <http://nwm.gov.in/>.
- Oberć, Barbara Pia, and Schnell, Alberto Arroyo. 2020. Approaches to sustainable agriculture. International Union for Conservation of Nature, IUCN, Brussels. <https://portals.iucn.org>.
- Paroda R, Crispino L, Minhaj A, Krishnakumar J, Ubalihero E, Jørgensen HJ and Balasubramanian N 2022. Sustainable agriculture and food systems in the global south: An Indian perspective. <https://echonetnetwork.pub>
- PSA. Office of the Principal Scientific Adviser 2020. National mission on biodiversity and human wellbeing. <https://www.psa.gov.in>.
- Anupam S and Verma P 2017. Factors influencing Indian consumers' actual buying behaviour towards organic food products. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 167:473-483.
- UNICEF, WHO. World Health Organization, and Group, World Bank. 2021. Levels and trends in child malnutrition: key findings of the 2021 edition of the joint child malnutrition estimates. <https://www.who.int>.
- Wenger-Trayner E, and Wenger-Trayner B 2015. Introduction to communities of practice. <https://wenger-trayner.com>